

A New Synthesis of ψ -Baptigenin

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A new synthesis of ψ -baptigenin was effected by acylation of piperidine enamine of homopiperonal with 2,4-diacetoxybenzoyl chloride followed by cyclization.

MOST isoflavone syntheses proceed *via* a desoxybenzoin which is prepared under fairly acidic conditions. These acidic conditions rather limit the type of protective groups used for ring B hydroxyl functions. Recently Uchiyama and Matsui¹ described a new approach to the synthesis of isoflavones and 2-hydroxy-isoflavones. Masaki, Uchiyama, Ooba and Kazumasa² applied the method in the synthesis of DL-Maackiain. The Japanese method avoids strongly acidic conditions and thus may permit a wider choice of acid sensitive protective groups. In the present work, the method has been used for the synthesis of ψ -baptigenin (I).

2,4-Diacetoxybenzoyl chloride (II)^{3,4} was condensed with the piperidine enamine (III) of homopiperonal in dry chloroform in presence of triethylamine. The intramolecular cyclization of the condensation product afforded ψ -baptigenin (I). The structure was confirmed by analysis, m.p., spectral data as well as by the formation of *o*-methyl ether (IV) and the *o*-acetate derivatives (V). The enamine (III) was obtained from homopiperonal by azeotropic refluxing with piperidine in dry benzene. Homopiperonal was obtained from piperonal according to a known procedure⁵.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on Kofler hot stage apparatus and uncorrected. U.V. spectra were taken on Beckman DB-G double beam (recording model)

grating spectrophotometer. I.R. spectra were taken on Unicam SP 1000 infra red spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 NMR spectrophotometer (TMS as internal reference).

2,4-Diacetoxybenzoyl Chloride (II): A mixture of β -resorcylic acid (25 g.), acetyl chloride (62.5 ml) was refluxed on water bath at 50°-55° for 5 hr and then gradually cooled. The separated 2,4-diacetoxybenzoic acid was collected, washed with ether to remove the excess acetyl chloride. Recrystallised from benzene in colourless crystals. Yield 25 g (71%) m.p. 136° (lit.⁵ m.p. 136°) (Found: C, 55.5, H, 4.15; Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₆, C, 55.46; H, 4.20%). I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ cm⁻¹ 1782 (ester C=O), 1695 (acid C=O), 1620 (Arom. C=C), no phenolic OH absorption. NMR (DMSO) δ : 2.3 (6H, s, 2 CH₃-CO-O-); 7.25, and 8.0 (each 1H, each d, (J = 2.5 cps and J = 8 cps, C₅-H and C₆-H); 7.1 (1H, s, C₃-H).

A mixture of 2,4-diacetoxy benzoic acid (10 g), thionyl chloride (15 ml.) was refluxed over water bath at 70°-80° for 3 hr. The excess thionyl chloride was removed in vacuum. The liquid was distilled to get the acid chloride, B.P. 170°/12 mm. I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Liq. film}}$ cm⁻¹ 1800 (acid chloride C=O), 1585 (arom. C=C).

Homopiperonal: A solution of piperonal (54 g., 1.8 mols) and methyl chloroacetate (47 ml., 2.7 mols) was slowly added (during a period of 3 hr) under stirring to sodium, (12.42 g., 2.7 g. atom) in dry methanol (180 ml.) chilled to -10° in an ice salt bath. After the addition of the mixture the stirring was continued for 2 hr at -5° and left overnight at room temperature. The mixture was poured into ice water (700 ml.) containing acetic acid (4 ml.). The separated white glycidate was collected, washed with cold water, dried in a vacuum dessicator, yield 65 g (90%), and recrystallised from methanol to give lumpy crystals of methyl -3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-glycidate m.p. 64° (lit.⁵ m.p. 65°) (Found: C, 59.50; H, 3.61; Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₅, C, 59.45; H, 3.50%) I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ cm⁻¹ 1755 (ester C=O). NMR (CCl₄) δ : 3.75 (3H, s, COO-CH₃);

5.95 (2H, s, -O-CH₂-O-); 3.3 (1H, d, J = 1.4 cps, -C-CH-COO-); 3.9 (1H, d, J = 1.6 cps, Ph-HC-C-);
 $\begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{6.65 (1H, C}_6\text{-H); 6.75 (2H, C}_2\text{-H, C}_5\text{-H).} \end{array}$

The methyl glycidate (32 g., 1.44 mols) in dry benzene (180 ml.) was added to methanolic sodium methoxide (3.4 g. sodium, 1.48 g. atom) in dry methanol (48 ml) at 5° on the stirring condition and ether (100 ml) containing water (3 ml) was added and kept at 5°-10° for 3 hr. The product, sodium-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-glycidate was collected by filtration, washed with ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Yield 32.1 g (96.5%). The crude sodium glycidate (17 g., 0.41 mols) was suspended in dry benzene (100 ml) and stirred. Acetic acid (4.5 g., 0.41 mols) was added, and kept in the stirred and refluxed condition for 3 hr while CO₂ gas was being evolved. The reaction mixture was left over night at room temperature. Water was added. The aqueous layer was extracted with benzene. The extract was mixed with the main benzene layer, washed with water and dried by anhydrous MgSO₄. On evaporation of benzene, the crude oil left was vacuum distilled to get the pure homopiperonal (7 g.) b.p. 98°/8 mm (bath temp. 190°-200°). I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{liq. film}}$ cm⁻¹ 1725 (aldehydic, C = O); 1615 (arom. C = C). NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 3.55 (2H, q, Ph-CH₂-C = O); 5.9 (2H, s, -O-CH₂-O-); 6.7 (3H, m, C₁-H); 9.65 (1H, m, -CHO).

Piperidine enamine of homopiperonal (III): A solution of homopiperonal (3.3 g), piperidine (2.1 g), *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (32 mg) in dry benzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr with azeotropic separation of water. After cooling the reaction mixture the solvent was removed by evaporation in the rotary evaporator. Dry benzene was added to the red syrupy liquid and concentrated in the rotary evaporator to get the crude red thick liquid enamine (4.5 g). I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{liq. film}}$ cm⁻¹ 1640 (-CH = CH-) and no C = O absorption.

ψ -baptigenin (I): Triethylamine (2.1 g) and dry chloroform (12 ml) were added to the crude enamine (III). 2,4-diacetoxybenzoyl chloride (4.6 g) in dry chloroform (10 ml) was added dropwise to the stirred enamine mixture at ice bath temperature. The mixture was stirred for 6 hr at the same temperature and left overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was concentrated in the rotary evaporator. Dry benzene was added and the precipitate of triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off and the filtrate was again concentrated in the rotary evaporator to get the dark red syrupy liquid condensation product.

Pyridine (30 ml), water (6 ml) and piperidine (30 ml) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was concentrated on the rotary evaporator giving a dark red thick liquid which was extracted with aqueous sodium hydroxide, filtered and the filtrate on acidification gave the crude pseudobaptigenin. On recrystallisation from a large volume of ethanol yielded crystals of ψ -baptigenin (I). Yield (1.2 g.) m.p. 294° (d) (lit.⁶ m.p. 292°-93°) (Found: C, 68.04; H, 3.58; Calc. for C₁₆H₁₀O₅, C, 68.08; H, 3.54%). U.V. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ nm (ϵ) 222 (16810), 250 (16345), 262 (sh), 295 (11720), 344 (sh.). I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ cm⁻¹ 3152 (W) (phenolic OH), 1630 (S) (γ -pyrone C = O), 1621 (S), 1600 (S), 1575 (S), 1492 (S) (Arom. C = C). NMR: (CDCl₃) δ : 6.0 (2H, s, -O-CH₂-O-), 7.1 (5H, m, C-2',5',6',6,8-H); 8.0 (1H, s, C-2-H); 8.25 (1H, d, J = 8 cps, C₅-H).

ψ -baptigenin-o-methylether (IV): Crystallised from ethanol giving short needles. Yield (0.4 g) m.p. 182° (lit.⁶ m.p. 180°) (Found: C, 68.99; H, 4.15; Calc. for C₁₇H₁₂O₅, C, 68.91; H, 4.05%). U.V. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{Ethanol}}$ nm (ϵ) 223 (25040), 249 (20580), 263 (20880), 293 (16830). I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ cm⁻¹ 1636 (γ -pyrone C = O), 1625, 1607, 1573, 1484 (arom. C = C). NMR: (CDCl₃) δ : 3.9 (3H, s, CH₃O-); 5.95 (2H, s, -O-CH₂-O-); 7.0 (5H, m, C-2',5',6',6,8-H); 7.9 (1H, s, C₂-H); 8.2 (1H, d, J = 8 cps, C₅-H).

ψ -baptigenin-o-acetate (V): Crystallised from alcohol (0.3 g.) m.p. 176° (lit.^{6,7} m.p. 176°, 165°) (Found: C, 66.68; H, 3.74; Calc. for C₁₈H₁₂O₆; C, 66.66; H, 3.70%). I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ cm⁻¹ 1641 (C = O), 1656 (acetate C = O).

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